

Static Elastomeric Seal Developments in Oil Field Exploration

Final Technical Report

MAT 7400 – Research and Design Team Project 2016/17

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PART A (AA, KK, NM, SL)

Introducing the Research Problem

The ubiquitous usage of petroleum hydrocarbons, coupled with the challenges encountered during their extraction, demands the use of highly developed equipment capable of delivering seamless performance. Constituting fundamental components of the technical apparatus, seals fulfil various functions essential to the operation, from the maintenance of an appropriate sealing force, to the prevention of unwanted leakages (Wei et al., 2013 & Cabrera et al., 2016). Operating in harsh environments, the litany of conditions to be mitigated against includes: pressures up to 20,000 psi or 137 MPa, temperatures ranging from -50°C to 180°C and the presence of malignant fluids and gases. Such factors necessitate the usage of adequate materials, with the preferred choice being elastomers, specifically, nitrile butadiene rubber (NBR), hydrogenated nitrile butadiene rubber (HNBR) and fluoroelastomers (FKM). With each possessing high elongation at yield, the subtle differences between them relate to their high temperature capabilities and chemical resistance (Callister, 2015), particularly their susceptibility to swelling in certain fluids. The ultimate distinguishing feature of an elastomer is the capacity for large, recoverable deformation. Polymeric materials comprised of covalently bonded hydrogen and carbon repeat units, this backbone forms molecular chains with their abundance and subsequent rotation ensuring entanglements arise throughout the material (Saalwächter, 2005 & Ngai, 1994). Upon extension of these chains, there is a reduction in the number of possible conformations leading to a decreased entropy; this provides a restoring force enabling return of the elastomer to its original state (Treloar, 1975). The repeat units of the named elastomers are shown in Figure 1. Viscoelastic in nature, elastomers display time-dependent strain behaviour. The mechanical properties of elastomers may be improved through the addition of fillers such as carbon black, or by crosslinking the material through vulcanisation. Positioned at integral locations throughout the structure, replacement of a faulty or malfunctioning seal requires shutdown of the drilling platform, resulting in substantial economic losses, with failure bearing consequences far more damaging; thus, the service life of these components is a fundamental feature of the application.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of: a) nitrile butadiene rubber and b) fluoro elastomer

Fluorination of Elastomers

Surface treatment methods are typically employed in cases where it is desirable to modify the surface properties of a material, whilst maintaining the characteristic bulk properties. Concerning usage of rubber seals in the oil and gas industry, fluorination is the predominant surface treatment, with multiple techniques available. Direct exposure of the target surface to a gaseous mixture of fluorine and inert gas leads to the disruption of C-H bonds and saturation of C=C double bonds as they react with molecular fluorine and fluororadicals in a radical chain process, forming C-F, C-F₂ and C-F₃ moieties (Kharitonov et al., 2007). The high exothermicity of the elementary stages permits the process to proceed at room temperature, with no catalyst or hazardous organic solvent required; thermal activation yields an enhanced level of fluorination as the F/C atomic ratio increases from 1.2 to 1.86, as further saturation of the butadiene double bonds occurs (Tressaud et al., 2004). A second technique is radiofrequency (rf) plasma fluorination. A fluorine source, typically CF₄ gas, is excited by an rf source, with the generated reacting species diffusing towards the sample found at the centre of the reaction chamber. Controlled parameters include temperature, pressure, rf power and CF₄ gas flow rate (Durand et al., 2004). A transient reaction zone (<< 0.1 μm) separates the modified layer from the unmodified bulk, with the depth of fluorination sometimes extending to 20 μm. Across all methods, the initial characteristics of the original elastomer and the environmental parameters controlled during the experiment can vary the nature of the bonds formed. Fluorination has been shown to influence a plethora of important properties, from surface energy and biocompatibility, to mechanical behaviours and chemical stability (Schlögl et al., 2011 & Vega-Cantu et al., 2002). The efficacy of fluorination in improving the features of an elastomer pertinent to their application as seals is often invoked to buttress use of the technique; a key feature being the frictional behaviour of the material.

Friction and Fluorination

The frictional behaviour of an elastomer is intimately related to its longevity as a seal. Dynamic seals are those engaged in motion relative to the mating surfaces, whilst static seals function in

situations where the mating surfaces experience no relative motion. Frictional behaviour can impinge on the elastomer through increasing susceptibility to abrasion and wear, damaging the component, hindering its performance (Xu et al., 2009) and rendering estimations on the expected service life unreliable due to uncertainty about the condition of the seal. Administration of fluorination is aimed at ameliorating this predicament by reducing the coefficient of friction, amongst a host of other intentions, including increasing resistance to swelling by liquids and gases (Huang, 2014).

Project Aims and Objectives (AA)

Aims

The primary aim of this project is to investigate the quantifiable differences in the slow-speed frictional behaviour of fluorinated and non-fluorinated elastomers (NBR and FKM), substantiating the subsequent comparison in a theoretical framework. This includes the measurement of their coefficient of friction, amongst a host of other properties pertinent to developing a comprehensive understanding of the impact of fluorination on these materials. These properties include hardness, modulus and surface energy. The levels of fluorination range from the untreated Level 0, to Level 5 and Level 9 treatment. A secondary aim relates to the methods employed to achieve the first, which are the use of both micro and macro friction testing. Evaluation of the results obtained from each method may provide insight into the merits of each, enabling a rigorous comparison of the two materials. Moreover, a tertiary aim will be the demonstration of an adequately functioning macro friction test rig, capable of delivering results suitable for analysis in such an investigation.

Objectives

Supporting these aims are multiple project objectives. Firstly, the design and construction of a macro friction testing rig is necessary for the collection of data, with establishment of an appropriate experimental procedure essential in validating the methodology. Facilitating accommodation of the testing rig into an environmental chamber and ensuring the application of a known normal load are the two major considerations shaping the design process. From this, a fundamental objective is the performance of the slow-speed sliding friction tests, supplying the required data for completion of the primary aim. Secondly, information gathered from various materials characterisation techniques will support the theoretical understanding presented. A wide range of microscopy studies will provide information on the surface morphology and topography, with Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) supplying

information on the chemical composition of each sample. Contact angles measurements used to determine the surface energies. As mentioned, consolidation of the information derived from the various tests and techniques will be used to forward an explanation of the frictional behaviours of these elastomers, as it relates to fluorination and the oil and gas industry.

Overview of Methods (AA)

Prior to specifying the principle findings, outcomes and conclusions of the project, the methods adopted ensuring their completion are incorporated into a brief description of Part B – the main technical report covering the work conducted by the team throughout this project.

Introducing Part B

A work-package flowchart illustrating management of the project and the steps taken towards its completion is presented. The design and construction of the macro test rig is reviewed, with specific details on the considerations made during this phase and an evaluation of the actual functioning of the rig. Following this are detailed descriptions of the tests performed throughout the study, from macro and micro friction testing, to materials characterisation techniques such as confocal microscopy (CM) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). A short section expounding on the use of MATLAB coding for results analysis is also included. Commenting on the data and information gathered from these various investigations, the discussion expresses a coherent account on the impact fluorination has on the frictional behaviour of the examined elastomers, concluding on the potential for enhancement with the surface treatment.

Principal Findings, Outcomes and Conclusions (AA)

- Obtaining the macro frictional behaviour required the design and manufacture of a novel friction test rig. A two-pulley system was designed due to the space limitation within the environmental chamber for temperature testing, therefore allowing to increase sliding distance.
- All fluorinated samples demonstrated a lower rubber coefficient of friction relative to their non-treated samples, in macro friction testing. A Level 5 (medium) fluorination demonstrated a lower rubber friction relative to Level 9 (high) fluorinated samples.
- All fluorinated samples demonstrated a lower rubber coefficient of friction relative to their non-treated samples, in micro friction testing. Level 9 (high) fluorinated samples displayed the lowest rubber friction relative to both Level 5 and non-treated.
- Under microscale friction, higher sliding velocity will lead to a higher rubber friction.
- Under microscale friction, higher temperature will lead to a lower rubber friction.
- From the results from the microscopy study, higher fluorinated samples displayed a greater degree of micro-cracks. Micro-line roughness increases with higher level fluorination.

PART B

1. Work Package Flowchart (AA)

This section details the individual contributions to the project from each group member, listing their roles and responsibilities in Table B.1; Table B.2 presents the various phases completed throughout the year, describing the activities and specific features of each phase.

Table B.1: Individual contributions	
Group Member	Roles and Responsibilities
Anas Achi (AA)	Materials characterisation Macro friction testing Quality control of all documents
Kamiar Karbasioun (KK)	Design and manufacture of macro friction test rig Macro friction testing Quality control of all documents
Nikesh Mandalia (NM)	Organiser of meetings and lab sessions Design and manufacture of macro friction test rig Macro friction testing
Shibai Liao (SL) Group Leader	Strategic decisions Micro friction testing Materials characterisation

Table B.2: Comprehensive overview of project			
Phase	Activity	Feature	Responsibility
Concept Phase	Development of aims and objectives	Communicate with Cameron	All
	Examination of current rig designs		All
	Understanding of CoF procedure		All
Design Phase	Brainstorm possible designs	Materials selection	KK and NM
		Performance estimations	
	Evaluation and confirmation of proposed design	CAD model developed with SolidWorks	KK and NM
	Manufacture of macro friction testing rig	Procurement of materials and components	KK and NM

SOTA Phase	Decide upon themes to be discussed	Discussion with project supervisors		All
	Literature review of subject area	Sections allocated to each member for research		All
	Outline of structure			All
	Write SOTA			All
Materials Characterisation Phase	Confocal Microscopy			SL
	Scanning Electron Microscopy			SL
	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy			AA
	Contact Angle Measurements			AA
	Atomic Force Microscopy			SL
Testing Phase	Macro Friction Testing	Sample test runs	Practice procedure	KK and NM
			Determine appropriate conditions (load and sample size)	
	Macro Friction Testing	Varying speeds and temperatures		AA, KK and NM
	Micro Friction Testing			SL
Analysis Phase	Analysis of results	Extensive reading on subject matter		All
Report Phase	Outline of structure	Discussion with project supervisors		All
	Integration of various phases	Communication amongst group members		All

2. Macro Friction Test (KK & NM)

2.1 Introduction (KK)

This section outlines the study undertaken to investigate the macro-frictional properties of the elastomers listed in Table B.3. Firstly, the design and manufacturing process of the novel friction test rig is presented. Secondly, the data obtained pertinent to the frictional properties of these elastomers is presented, and a discussion of the results is provided with respect to each tested elastomer, fluorination level and sliding velocity. The discussion further extends to evaluating the procedure implemented and the friction test rig. Finally, this section deliberates on the implementation of potential future work towards the betterment of macro friction testing.

Table B.3: Elastomers investigated with fluorination levels	
Elastomer	Fluorination Level
NBR #10	0 (no treated)
	5
	9
FKM #8	0 (no treated)
	5
	9
FKM #2	0 (no treated)
	9

2.2 Manufacturing the Test Rig (KK)

Figure 2 illustrates a Computer Aided Design (CAD) model of the proposed friction test rig. Accommodation of the test rig into an already existing environmental chamber was the first major consideration during the design and manufacture phase. The exposure of the rig to temperatures ranging from -50 °C to 150 °C necessitated the usage of materials capable of maintaining suitable dimensions in spite of the anticipated thermal expansion. Materials selection research and performance estimations led to the use of aluminium and mild steel for the manufacture of the test rig. In-depth discussion of this phase can be found in the SOTA.

Figure 2: CAD design of macro friction test rig

Before starting the design and manufacture of the friction rig, all the dimensions were measured carefully. By getting advice from experts and putting all the requirements together, the best design for the friction rig was chosen and the material selection and ordering process was done.

The materials used in the manufacture are listed below:

- Pulley: Deep groove ball bearing (17 x 40 x 12 mm)
- Base: Aluminium plate (10 mm thickness, 220 mm width and 230 mm length)
- Sliding Surface: Aluminium plate (4 mm thickness, mm width and mm length)
- Pulley support: Aluminium angle (20 x 20 mm)
- Pulley support: OD mild steel rod (17 mm outer diameter)
- Sled: Aluminium sheet (4 mm thickness, 150 mm width and 195 mm length)

The manufacturing process started with cutting the main base of the rig to the desired size. Figure 3 shows this, as the base was cut into a rectangle with length of 230 mm and a width of 220 mm. This size was chosen for the base by taking into consideration all the expansion the base would go through at high temperatures and for the best fit in the environmental chamber.

The majority of the cutting for the base was done using a table saw machine and for the smaller and more precise cuts a milling machine was used.

Figure 3: The base of the test rig being cut using a milling machine

After the main base was cut to the required size, the holes for the stands of the pulleys were drilled in the correct position. The stands were positioned in such a way that the central pulley is positioned directly below the top opening of the environmental chamber. This is important in order to reduce any additional friction, reducing detrimental effects to the accuracy of future calculations. Each stand was made from two aluminium L shaped trim screwed to each other. In order to hold the pulleys in place with the stands, two mild steel rods were used and the pulleys were fixed onto the rods.

Figure 4: Pulleys and stands

Figure 5: Circular stand and adaptor for test rig

A deep groove ball bearing was used as a pulley for the friction test rig. This pulley was chosen specifically since it can handle high tension and temperatures that was required for our testing. In order to stop the string slipping of the sides of the pulley two O-ring rubbers were fitted on either side of the pulley in order to keep the string in place. Next part of the manufacturing process is the circular base holding the rig to the Instron machine. In order to make the test rig stay fixed to the environmental chamber and the Instron machine, it was necessary to design a rigid stand. The stand is shown in Figure 5 and is made out of two parts. The first part of the design is the supporting disc. This part is mounted to the main base of the rig by eight screws and it can withstand the external forces applied to the test rig, such as the force from the applied deadweight. The second part is the cylinder adapter, this component is attached to the Instron machine, and is then further supported via a pin that slots through the hole at the bottom. This part holds the test rig in place throughout the experiment, therefore manufacturing the component to suit the Instron machine is critical. The stand required high accuracy cut and finish and therefore for this specific part, a 3D CAD model was given to the lab technicians and the stand was done using automatic machines. Moreover, all the materials needed for this specific part was already available at QMUL facilities and therefore these materials have not been listed above. For the cylinder part of the stand the height was calculated to be 85 mm and the diameter of 31.75 mm. The bigger circular part has a thickness of 20 mm and a diameter of 100 mm. Eight holes were drilled into the base section for the screws each with a diameter of 11 mm.

Figure 6: Completed macro friction test rig

2.3 Preamble to Macro Friction Results (NM)

This section explains an experimental study investigating the macro frictional properties of the elastomers supplied by Cameron. The aim of the experimental procedure is first, to assess the influence of both fluorination and sliding velocity has onto the frictional properties, second, evaluating the frictional test rig and the experimental procedure used. Three unique materials labelled as FKM #2, FKM #8, and NBR #10 were tested with a varying surface fluorination level namely, Level 0 (no surface treatment), Level 5 and Level 9. Fluorination is a widely-adopted surface modification technique on elastomers, resulting in a reduction in the coefficient of friction and enhanced barrier properties relative to a non-fluorinated specimen. It is therefore expected materials that have been fluorinated exhibit a lower coefficient of friction, however the relationship between fluorination level and coefficient of friction value is unknown.

A central design feature of the friction test rig was the compatibility with the Instron environmental chambers at Queen Mary University of London, therefore allowing frictional properties to be obtained at varying temperature conditions. For the macro friction tests, a prepared sample of contact dimension 20x20mm was attached to a sled, then subsequently pressed onto the aluminium substrate via the application of a normal load from a 1kg deadweight, as shown in Figure 7. The sample was hauled across the substrate over a 100mm

length, the sliding velocity was kept constant throughout each test either at 0.1mm/s or 1mm/s.

Figure 7 : Schematic of the friction test rig (not to scale). A deadweight of mass 1kg provided the normal force, with the elastomer moving at sliding velocity of 0.1mm/s or 1mm/s

2.4 Macro Friction Results (NM, KK)

2.4.1 Frictional Behaviour at different fluorination levels and sliding velocities

In this section the main findings from the macro friction test are presented, specifically the coefficient of friction with respect to fluorination level and sliding velocity for FKM #2, FKM #8 and NBR #10. All tests were completed at 23°C, however, the ambient relative humidity was not controlled. To determine the coefficient of friction values, firstly raw data for the frictional force was obtained through an Instron universal testing machine, this device enforced the sliding velocity of the sledge whilst measuring the frictional force between the elastomer and substrate. The frictional force was then divided by the normal reaction force which accounted for both the deadweight and weight of the sledge. Raw data of the frictional force plotted against the sliding distance is presented in appendix.

To obtain the coefficient of friction, the frictional force values were extracted between a sliding distance of 75 mm and 85 mm, this follows an analysis into determining appropriate regions where all data sets reach steady state with the frictional force for a sufficient sliding distance. A typical relationship between frictional force measured and sliding distance is presented: firstly, between 0 mm and 30 mm the friction test rig starts to build tension within the wire

whilst the elastomer attains an increasing frictional force (0-20mm), once the tension within the wire is equivalent to the frictional force it takes a further distance from circa 20 mm to 30 mm to approach steady state. Further to this, due to a non-uniformity of the substrate between

Figure 8: Plot of the coefficient of friction for FKM #2, FKM #8 and NBR #10 with varying surface fluorination levels and sliding speed.

40 mm and 60 mm, the frictional force alters in this region, and then fully recovers to steady state before 70 mm. This process is evidently displayed with the coefficient of friction against sliding distance plot for FKM #2, Level 0 at 0.1 mm/s with Figure 9.

In this study, two types of friction behaviour were observed, namely steady sliding and stick-slip. For steady sliding, the coefficient of friction values was taken as the average continuous value between 75-85 mm for the reason explained. In contrast, for elastomers displaying stick-slip behaviour the peak values for each ‘stick-slip’ motion was recorded and then averaged between the same region. This peak coefficient of friction was selected as this indicates the maximum value required to enable any motion between the paired surface, thus directly relating to the frictional force experienced during the phenomenon of stick-slip.

Table B.4: Coefficients of Friction (CoF) for FKM #2, FKM #8 and NBR #10 at varying fluorination levels and sliding velocities			
Fluorination Grade	Sliding Velocity		% change in CoF (from 0.1mm/s)^B
	0.1mms/	1mm/s	

FKM #2			
0	2.18	2.20	1%
9	1.65	1.56	-6%
% change in CoF (from Level 0)^A	-24%	-29%	

FKM #8			
0	2.37	2.10	-11%
5	1.58	1.49	-6%
% change in CoF (from Level 0)^A	-33%	-29%	
9	1.72	1.66	-4%
% change in CoF (from Level 0)^A	-27%	-21%	

NBR #10			
0	2.03	2.35	16%
5	0.35	0.29	-17%
% change in CoF (from Level 0)^A	-83%	-88%	
9	0.64	0.66	3%
% change in CoF (from Level 0)^A	-69%	-72%	

A: Percentage change in the coefficient of friction value relative to the non-fluorinated sample (Level 0), whilst at the same sliding velocity.

B: Percentage change in the coefficient of friction relative to the value measured for 0.1mm/s sliding velocity, whilst at the same fluorination level.

A distinct trend is demonstrated for the three elastomers tested, fluorinated samples (both Level 5 and Level 9) exhibited a lower coefficient of friction relative to the non-fluorinated elastomer (Level 0). This is shown in Figure 8, which plots the three types of elastomers studied alongside each fluorination level and sliding velocity tested. More interestingly, considering the average coefficient of friction, this reduces when adopting a Level 5 surface fluorination for both FKM #8 and NBR #10 (as FKM #2 with Level 5 fluorination was not present) from the non-fluorinated equivalent, however adopting a higher fluorination grade (Level 9) adversely affected the coefficient of friction values, as this value increases for both FKM #8 and NBR #10 relative to the Level 5 fluorination equivalence.

The frictional force of elastomers is widely known to originate from following three mechanisms: adhesion occurring between the paired surface, hysteresis arising from bulk deformation, and wear of the elastomer. The adhesion process is formed following the bond development between the surfaces of the elastomer and substrate, categorised as a viscoelastic

process (Schallamach 1971), as adhesion being dependent on the true contact area between the paired surface, an increased number of bonds will occur with a greater true contact area. Furthermore, firstly exhibiting a viscoelastic process yields a mechanism to dissipate energy, forming as the elastomer surface deforms as it is hauled across the asperity containing substrate, consequently penetrating into the bulk of the material. Second, regions of the elastomer in direct contact these asperities, i.e. on the outer surface, experience significant deformation thus yielding higher viscoelastic losses. Thirdly, losses are present due to nature of creating and breaking of bonds between the substrate and elastomer, and fourthly, a wear type mechanism as loose particles are detached from the elastomer bulk, therefore, contributing to energy losses (Lorenz et al. 2011). All these four aspects will contribute to the overall frictional force, and any reduction in the energy dissipation may yield a reduction in the coefficient of friction. The materials investigated in this research had a varying fluorination level from Level 0 (non-fluorinated), 5 and 9, it is therefore expected the reduction in the coefficient of friction was led by a favourable change in the viscoelasticity at the surface and an extent within the material bulk, therefore adopting the use of fluorination has led to a reduction in the viscoelastic energy losses and has consequently yielded a reduction in frictional forces.

2.4.2 Frictional Behaviour and Fluorination – FKM #2

With regards to FKM# 2, two unique materials were examined, a non-fluorinated (Level 0) and a Level 9 fluorinated version. For both sliding velocities, a notable reduction in the coefficient of friction was demonstrated, as shown in Figure 8 and Table B.4. A 24 % and 29 % reduction in average value was recorded, corresponding to an absolute coefficient of friction reduction from 2.18 to 1.65 and 2.20 to 1.56 for 0.1 mm/s and 1 mm/s sliding velocities respectively. The frictional behaviour on all tests displayed steady sliding except for the Level 0 specimen at a sliding velocity of 1 mm/s.

Increasing the sliding velocity has led to an insignificant change in the average coefficient of friction value measured, especially for the non-fluorinated sample, this displayed a 1 % increase, as the sliding velocity increased to 1 mm/s from 0.1 mm/s. Furthermore, the Level 9 sample exhibited a 6 % decrease in value.

Figure 9: Coefficient of friction plotted for FKM #2, non-fluorinated, at a sliding velocity of 0.1mm/s, demonstrating steady sliding frictional behaviour

2.4.3 Frictional Behaviour and Fluorination – FKM #8

A reduction in the coefficient of friction for fluorinated specimens was recorded, relative to the non-fluorination equivalent. For this material set, three unique variants were tested namely, level 0 (non-fluorinated), level 5 and level 9 fluorination. A reduction in the friction coefficient of 33 % and 29 % for level 5 fluorination, and a reduction of 27 % and 21 % for level 9 fluorination were measured with respect to level 0 for a sliding velocity of 0.1 mm/s and 1 mm/s respectively. Interestingly, the FKM #8 fluorinated at level 9 resulted in a higher coefficient of friction value relative to the corresponding values for level 5 fluorination; it is proposed that the highest level of fluorination has resulted in adversely influencing surface properties with regards to frictional properties. It is known fluorination results in the development of microcracks on the surface (Vega-Cantú et al. 2003), therefore with increasing fluorination, it is expected the severity of these microcracks increase. This has a higher chance to adversely interact with the asperities on the substrate, subsequently leading to increased frictional losses due to the formation and propagation of cracks. This material demonstrated an 11 % decrease in coefficient of friction for Level 0, as the sliding velocity was increased from 0.1 mm/s to 1 mm/s. Furthermore, both fluorinated versions displayed a reduction in the coefficient of friction value of 6 % and 4 % respectively.

2.4.4 Frictional Behaviour and Fluorination – NBR #10

Likewise with FKM 8, three variants of NBR #10 with varying levels of fluorination were tested, namely Level 0 (non-fluorinated), Level 5 and Level 9 fluorination. Firstly, a notable reduction in the coefficient of friction is displayed, as shown in Figure 8 and Table B.4, for both fluorinated elastomers (Level 5 and 9) with respect to the non-fluorinated equivalent. A reduction of 83 % and 88 % for Level 5 and 69 % and 72 % for Level 9 fluorination with respect to the non-fluorinated elastomer was shown for a sliding velocity of 0.1 mm/s and 1 mm/s respectively. Increasing the sliding velocity had the most notable change of coefficient of friction relative to FKM #2 and FKM #8, namely for Level 0 and Level 5, as they displayed a 16 % increase and a 17 % decrease in value as the sliding velocity increased from 0.1 mm/s to 1 mm/s respectively. In contrast, Level 9 displays an insignificant increase (3 %) of the coefficient of friction with increasing sliding velocity.

Figures 10, 11 and 12 plots the coefficient of friction value against the distance the elastomer NBR #10 travelled on the substrate, at a sliding velocity of 1 mm/s for the non-fluorinated, Level 5 and Level 9 fluorination elastomers. Firstly, considering the friction behaviour, for the non-fluorinated (Level 0) sample this was stick-slip, thereafter this behaviour changes to a steady-state sliding once the samples were fluorinated for both Level 5 and Level 9 types. Therefore, the application of the fluorinated layer has changed the frictional behaviour, hence a change in the viscoelastic behaviour at the surface is expected, this is also complimented with a reduction in the coefficient of friction. Both these factors favour the onset of steady sliding. Similarly with the FKM #2 elastomers observing steady sliding frictional behaviour, these displayed a notable alteration, as shown with Figure 11 and 12. Therefore, with the steady sliding behaviour, the actual surface quality is critical in determining the coefficient of friction, such that any defect present on the surface will lead to a notable change in value relative to the stick-slip friction behaviour.

Figure 10: Coefficient of friction plotted for NBR #10, non-fluorinated (level 0) at a sliding velocity of 1mm/s, demonstrating stick-slip frictional behaviour

Figure 11: Coefficient of friction plotted for NBR #10, level 5 fluorinated, at a sliding velocity of 1mm/s, demonstrating steady sliding frictional behaviour.

Figure 12: Coefficient of friction plotted for NBR #10, level 9 fluorinated, at a sliding velocity of 1mm/s, demonstrating steady sliding frictional behaviour.

2.4.5 Surface non-uniformities

Surface defects were present on the substrate, the location of these defects was positioned on the sliding region where the elastomer was hauled across, namely between circa 40 mm and 60 mm. This led to a notable alteration of the coefficient of friction measured, principally with elastomers demonstrating steady sliding, as shown in Figure 9 (FKM #2, Level 0, at 0.1 mm/s), and with Figure 11 and 12 (NBR #10, Level 5 and 9), all test repeats demonstrated corresponding trends, therefore this has been attributed exclusively on the non-uniformity of the substrate and not the elastomeric sample. As the elastomers tested in this study was hauled across the substrate, it is expected the real contact area significantly changes especially in the region containing the non-uniformity. The connection between the real contact area and friction was envisaged by Schallamach (1952), indicating the frictional force is tightly related to the contact area between the paired surfaces. Moreover, Schallamach (1952) and Persson (1998) showed the relationship between the measured frictional force of elastomeric material with the contact area, applied loading and contact pressure. Subsequently, it is expected that these three parameters were altered in the region containing the non-uniformity, hence leading to the variation in the coefficient of friction.

2.4.6 Stick-Slip Friction

The theory of stick-slip friction, explained as the elastomeric sample and the substrate undergoes a periodic alteration of velocity as was shown with a number of friction tests conducted in this study, the phenomena occurring can be explained below (Busse 2012):

- Firstly, the elastomer is in contact and sticks with the substrate, no motion occurs and is analogous with static friction.
- Secondly, shear deformation is present as the elastomer remains attached and stationary with the substrate, whilst the upper surface of the elastomer is pulled towards the direction of motion.
- Thirdly, once the shear force attributed from shear deformation exceeds the maximum frictional force the elastomer detaches from the substrate, thus moving towards the direction of motion, this is termed as slip.
- Fourthly, after the elastomer slips, it becomes reattached with the substrate and thus sticking occurs due to the continual normal force acting from the deadweight.

The four steps listed above is consequently repeated numerous times over the distance the elastomer is hauled across the substrate. Furthermore, the stick-slip behaviour was complemented with acoustic noise, known as chattering. An important feature of stick-slip behaviour, as observed with elastomers within this macro friction test, is that a master-curve between the coefficient of friction and sliding velocity can be generated, a master curve has been developed for NBR #10 for the micro friction tests in Chapter 3. This curve follows the William, Landel & Ferry (WLF) model which is based on the phenomena that both time and temperature results in equivalent consequences due to the possession of viscoelastic properties. Furthermore, as noted by Grosch (1963), it is possible to derive a maximum peak value from a master-curve plotting the sliding velocity and coefficient of friction. The position of this value is related to the transition of frictional behaviour from steady sliding to stick-slip. Consequently, it is expected that elastomers experiencing stick-slip behaviour observe a negative relationship between the coefficient of friction and sliding velocity, such any increase in sliding velocity will result in a reduction in the coefficient of friction. Introducing this observation into the macro friction results reveals that FKM #2 with Level 0 and Level 5 fluorination, and NBR #10 with Level 0 and Level 5 fluorination illustrated a reduction in the coefficient of friction values once increasing the sliding velocity from 0.1 mm/s to 1 mm/s, thus agreeing with this theory as these three samples experienced stick-slip behaviour on both sliding velocities. In contrast, FKM #8 with level 9 fluorination revealed an increase in friction coefficient once the sliding velocity increased to 1 mm/s from 0.1 mm/s, this opposes theory, however it is predicted that with the highest level of fluorination being applied, the changes in surface condition resulted in notable alteration in the viscoelastic properties, hence adversely influencing frictional values.

Regarding the frictional behaviour observed for NBR #10 with Level 5 fluorination at a sliding velocity of 0.1 mm/s, as shown in Figure 13, due to the non-uniformity on the substrate as previously mentioned, this has led to a notable increase in the coefficient of friction within this region (40 mm to 60 mm). Interestingly stick-slip frictional behaviour was displayed with Test 2 and Test 3, and due to the non-uniformity of the substrate's surface, a transition from stick-slip to steady sliding is shown for the latter tests, the frictional behaviour reverts to stick-slip once the frictional value stabilises after the fluctuation in value experienced within the area containing the non-uniformity.

The experimental results for NBR #10 with Level 5 fluorination displays an expected reduction in the coefficient of friction as the sliding velocity was increased to 1 mm/s from 0.1 mm/s,

shown in Figure 11 and 13. Namely, an average coefficient of friction value of 1.58 for 0.1 mm/s, this reduces to 1.49 mm/s for 1 mm/s. Furthermore, the frictional behaviour changes from a ‘transitional’ stick-slip to completely steady sliding as the sliding velocity increased. This will suggest testing the sample at 0.1 mm/s with the current experimental friction test rig and procedure resulted in operating near the peak of the master curve, as both characteristics of a reduction in friction coefficient and transition characteristics in frictional behaviour were displayed.

Figure 13: Coefficient of friction plotted for NBR 10, level 5 fluorinated, at a sliding velocity of 1mm/s, demonstrating both steady sliding and stick-slip frictional behaviour

2.4.7 Procedure – Acetone Test

Acetone was used as a surface cleaner for both the elastomer specimen and the aluminium substrate, using this approach allowed to repeat tests on the same elastomer specimen. Consequently, it becomes important to understand the implication of using acetone, if any, onto the recorded frictional force. Thus, FKM #8 with Level 5 fluorination was investigated with regards to the time allowed for the acetone to evaporate before conducting a new test. A plot of varying evaporation time with respect to the measured frictional force recorded over a 100 mm sliding distance is plotted in Figure 14. As the specimen observed stick-slip friction on all tests, only the peak frictional force was extracted and plotted for each stick-slip phenomena. All tests in this section followed the procedure as listed in this chapter, however, the time after

cleaning the sample and placing this onto the substrate was varied between 2 mins and 15 mins, and not kept constant.

Figure 14: Plot of the frictional force for FKM 8, Level 5 fluorination with varying evaporation time for acetone prior testing

A clear trend is demonstrated in the Figure 14 for FKM #8 with Level 5 fluorination, as increasing the ‘evaporation time’ of the acetone after cleaning evidently returns a higher frictional force. Therefore, acetone is effectively acting as a lubricant between the rubber specimen and substrate. This frictional force increased with evaporation time only until 12 min, as leaving 15 mins to allow the acetone to evaporate returns an equivalent frictional force with 12 mins. This remark is further reinforced by examining the average frictional force across the sliding distance, as listed in Table B.5. In this table, three individual section of the sliding distance is examined, namely between 20-40 mm, 40-60 mm, and 60-80 mm, this is due to the frictional force increases with distance. Leaving FKM #8 with Level 5 fluorination for 12 mins of evaporation time following the acetone cleaning returns a friction force of 17.2 N, 17.2 N, and 17.6 N, whilst for 15mins these values are 17.1 N, 17.3 N, and 17.6 N for the 20-40 mm, 40-60 mm and 60-80 mm respectively.

Table B.5: Mean frictional force against the permitted evaporation time for the acetone, with varying sections of substrate			
Evaporation Time (mins)	Mean frictional force (N)		
	20-40mm (standard deviation)	40-60mm (standard deviation)	60-80mm (standard deviation)
2	13.3 (0.34)	13.8 (0.53)	14.4 (0.36)
5	14.1 (0.31)	14.5 (0.37)	14.7 (0.54)
7	15.3 (0.34)	15.6 (0.36)	16.3 (0.43)
9	16.8 (0.35)	16.9 (0.28)	17.4 (0.46)
12	17.2 (0.29)	17.2 (0.30)	17.6 (0.61)
15	17.1 (0.38)	17.3 (0.33)	17.6 (0.54)

2.5 Friction Rig Evaluation (KK & NM)

To initiate testing, numerous preliminary tests were completed to develop a testing procedure which was compatible with the equipment and facilities at Queen Mary University of London.

Two individual materials, HNBR and FKM, which was not provided by Cameron was used for this preliminary test. The following parameters were varied to develop the macro friction test procedure that was ultimately used for the provided elastomeric samples:

- Specimen Dimension: 20 x 20 mm and 40 x 40 mm
- Sliding Velocity: 0.1 mm/s and 1 mm/s
- Applied Loading: 4 N, 10 N and 14 N

2.5.1 Applied Loading

The specimen was pressed onto the substrate via a deadweight, as shown in Figure 7. As a result, the specimen must be loaded identically for each test and this loading force should be appropriate, the latter is with regards to the suitability of the frictional force and the load cell used to measure this value, additionally considering the geometry of the friction rig. Figure 15 plots the Coefficient of Friction the HNBR specimen whilst having a dimension of 20 x 20 mm at a sliding velocity of 1 mm/s. The applied loading was altered via a 0.4 kg, 1 kg and 1.4 kg deadweight. It can be seen that an overall trend is demonstrated with the three configurations, that increasing the applied loading from 4 N to 14 N results in improved data, stability and reduction in noise. This large deviation of coefficient of friction value is due to the load cell recording a loading value of under 2 N, thus close the resolution of the component, consequently resulting in deviation in values. Furthermore, the contribution of the force from the bearing of the test rig is higher at lower load values. As it can be seen from the table below, increasing the applied loading to both 1 kg and 1.4 kg has resulted in significant improvement in data quality, as deviations are substantially reduced. For the applied load of 0.4 kg, mean of Test 1 and 2 established results of 0.38 and 0.27. This difference is much higher than the applied loads of 1 kg and 1.4 kg where the difference of mean is only 0.01. Furthermore, the standard deviation values for applied loads of 1 kg and 1.4 kg are much smaller than the one for a loading of 0.4 kg.

Figure 15: Plot of measured CoF for practise HNBR sample; dimensions of 20 x 20mm, with varying loading

Table B.6: Mean and Standard Deviation values for different applied loading conditions	
Applied Loading (kg)	Mean and Standard Deviation (20-60 mm)
0.4	Test 1: 0.38 (0.03) Test 2: 0.27 (0.04)
1	Test 1: 0.38 (0.01) Test 2: 0.39 (0.01)
1.4	Test 1: 0.44 (0.01) Test 2: 0.45 (0.01)

By carefully analysing the different results achieved by testing different specimen sizes at different speeds it was concluded that the 20x20 mm specimen size would be the best fit for the purpose of this project. One of the main reason for choosing this specimen size is that we were limited to the availability of samples. Therefore, using smaller samples for the testing was essential. Secondly, when applying the load to smaller samples, it can be assumed that all the sample is in full contact with the surface and more accurate results could be achieved as the contact stress is higher.

2.6.2 Contact Pressure

Figure 16: Comparison of CoF values for varying specimen dimensions. Differences attributed to changing contact areas and pressures

Figure 16 shows the difference in coefficients of friction for both 40 x 40 mm and 20 x 20 mm samples. A significant difference can be seen between the different sample sizes as 40 x 40 mm sample has an effective contact are of four times larger than the 20 x 20 mm sample, consequently resulting in a lower contact pressure between the substrate and elastomer. Additionally, it can be seen that the 40 x 40 mm sample did not reach steady state and the coefficient of friction continually increases with distance, therefore longer frictional test rig is needed for the 40 x 40 mm sample in order for it to reach steady state. Furthermore, the 20 x 20 mm sample reached the steady state between the distance of 40 mm and 60 mm.

Table B.7: Evaluation of the friction rig with regards to additional force from the bearings				
		Speed (mm/s)	Force (N)	% difference against Test A
Friction Rig	Test A	0.1	10.14	
	Test B	1	10.17	-0.3%
No Friction Rig*	Test C	0.1	9.96	-1.7%

2.6.3 Additional Force Contributions from Bearings

The friction rig was also evaluated with respect to the installed bearings, as this formed part of the pulley network. The evaluation particularly focused on the additional load the pulley system contributes towards the overall frictional force, as this was measured through the Instron load cell. To firstly examine the bearings, the wire used for each of the friction tests (for the provided elastomers: FKM #2, FKM #8 & NBR #10) was placed over the bearing as shown in Figure 17, and then tied to a 1 kg deadweight. The load was measured as the wire was hauled 100 mm of distance, effectively replicating the distance travelling during testing of the elastomeric specimens, both 0.1 and 1 mm/s velocities were tested. This is viewed as an additional force preventing the sliding motion of the elastomer, however the overall contribution was negligible (a 1.7 % increase in load) as listed in Table B.7.

All tests above were repeated 3 times, and an average value across the tests was taken once the force values approached steady state between 30 to 80 mm. Additionally, the evaluation tests were done by only using a loading of ~10 N (1 kg mass). However, using different loads the contributions from the bearings could have been dissimilar. For the friction tests, the results varied between 5 N to 25 N, whereas for the 10 N load the contribution from the bearings were 1.7 % and this value could change given that the bearings get tested under different loads.

Figure 17: Schematic of the procedure to measure the force contribution from the bearings

3. Micro Friction (SL)

As we know, majority of experiments which are designed to test frictional behaviour in rubber materials are under macroscopic scale (contact area is larger than 1 mm^2). Under large scale, frictional behaviours are tightly related to tyre industry and oil industry. In both these industries, macro scale friction will depend on saving energy for the whole system and extending service life of critical components. However, friction is not always showed as a bulk deformation and it is usually shown as a local deformation. Moreover, whether tiny scratches on a rubber surface will affect rubber properties needs to be further investigated. Besides the contribution to the industry, under microscopic scale, friction is also linked to the motion of polymer in scientific research. Thus, investigating micro scale frictional behaviour on rubber surface will both contribute to the industry aims and the scientific aims in this work.

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Equipment

Briefly, to extract the mechanical behaviour of rubber material in tiny scale, we normally use an already known geometry indenter coupled with obtained penetration depth to satisfy the experiment design. Nano Indenter has been invented in recent decades and vastly aroused the scientific researchers' interest. In this work, MicroMaterials® Nano Test Vintage equipment is used as the main micro scale friction testing machine, which is shown in Figure 18. Microscopic scale mechanical test is affected by many factors, such as surface roughness, initial penetration, thermal drift, instrument compliance, indenter geometry, and tip rounding. Thus, a constant experimental environment and a reliable testing machines are main problems. The principle of the test machine can be found in Figure 19. From the figure, we can find that there is a vacuum chamber which provide a good thermal isolation and stable environment. The temperature of the indenter and the sample are heated independently, which will avoid thermal gradient. Moreover, a pendulum system is used to obtain the travel depth and penetration depth. This system will ensure low thermal drift as well.

Figure 18: MicroMaterials® Nano Test Vintage equipment

Figure 19: Schematic of indenter-sample interaction

3.1.2 Procedure

Principally, the micro friction testing procedure can be described as the indenter is travelled along the rubber surface at a specific length under a normal force which is applied by equipment. Moreover, the velocity and the temperature can be adjusted by the software which

can control the test machine. Noted, during the test, sample stage is moving alongside x, y, z axis, but the indenter is fixed. The micro friction testing in this work is named as a ‘multiple passes’ method. The first pass is driven by a very tiny force ($< 1 \mu\text{N}$) and this pass is to scan the initial topography of rubber surface. The second pass is a ramped pass and do the real friction test under a pre-defined velocity and force. The third pass is the final scan of the topography which can compare the topography before and after the test.

To demonstrate in detail, the testing procedure, we take a micro friction test on FKM as an example. From Figure 20, the load applied onto the indenter is increased from 0 mN to 10 mN at the initial 200 μm length, then the load is maintained stably until the end of the test. The topography of the localised rubber surface then can be recorded by ‘multiple passes’ method, which can be observed from the figure below. The scratch depth can also be obtained after the second pass which can also be shown in Figure 20. Due to the ramped test, the friction force can be calculated from the normal force and the coefficient of friction can also be extracted from the dynamic friction theory. Thus, a typical FKM rubber sample’s micro friction test can be done. In this case, the indenter’s radius is 25 μm radii, so the contact pressure is about 88 MPa. Moreover, the lab used in this work is 23.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ constant and both of sample and indenter are kept in the same temperature which can be detected by Raman Spectrum or indentation on thermocouple. Thus, the results here are reliable and probably can be used as a future procedure to investigate different small scale or non-destructive mechanical test in a wide range of engineering materials.

Figure 20: Applied load, topography and scratch depth

3.2 Fluorination and Micro Friction

As mentioned in the former chapter, halogenation is a kind of surface treatment which is using F₂ other halogen gas to modify rubber surface by chemical reaction (Schlogl, 2011). The main aim of the fluorination process is to reduce the friction of the rubber surface. In order to fuller understand the effect of various fluorination level on different rubber materials, we use micro friction test to characterise the fluorination-rubber interaction. The details of samples are shown in Table B.8.

Table B.8: Specimen list			
Sample Name	Fluorination Level	Contac Area (μm^2)	Mean Pressure (MPa)
FKM #2	0 (no treated)	113.04	88.8
FKM #2	9	113.04	88.8
FKM #8	0 (no treated)	113.04	88.8
FKM #8	5	113.04	88.8
FKM #8	9	113.04	88.8
NBR #10	0 (no treated)	113.04	88.8
NBR #10	5	113.04	88.8
NBR #10	9	113.04	88.8

3.2.1 Fluorination – Room Temperature at Fixed Sliding Velocity

As mentioned above, fluorination will help to obtain ideally low friction coefficient. However, fluorination will increase the micro-roughness of the surface which will be detailed discussed later. Among all the specimens, rubber friction coefficient versus sliding distance at a fixed 100 $\mu\text{m/s}$ velocity and room temperature (23.5°C) will be examined firstly.

Figure 21: CoF vs Distance on FKM #2 no treated specimen

Figure 22: CoF vs Distance on FKM #2 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 23: CoF vs Distance on FKM #8 no treated specimen

Figure 24: CoF vs Distance on FKM #8 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 25: CoF vs Distance on FKM #8 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 26: CoF vs Distance on NBR #10 no treated specimen

Figure 27: CoF vs Distance on NBR #10 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 28: CoF vs Distance on NBR #10 fluorination level 9 specimen

As shown in all the graphs above, we can find that a clear Schallamach detachment wave can be observed. According to the literature (Barquins, 1986), contact area which is smaller than 12 mm^2 will lead to a Schallamach wave when the sliding velocity is higher than 100 um/s . From the plot of FKM #2 no treated specimen and FKM #2 fluorination level 9 specimen, we can find the rubber friction coefficient is approximately the same which does not show the same phenomenon under a macroscopic scale. Moreover, the data point is scattered, this is due to the line roughness of small area on rubber surface. From the observed rubber friction coefficient in FKM #8 with different level of fluorination, we can find the different level of fluorination will not affect microscopic rubber friction very much. More interesting thing is that both FKM #2 and FKM #8 are fluoroelastomer, and their coefficient of rubber friction are very similar, which may indicate that at microscopic scale, rubber friction is mainly affected

by material itself more than the surface roughness caused by fluorination. This can be verified by observed NBR #10 specimen. Rubber friction coefficient in NBR #10 is different in both two FKM samples. Furthermore, different rubber friction coefficient can be found in different fluorination level of NBR #10 samples. From above graphs, we can find that the CoF of NBR #10 no treated sample is smaller than NBR #10 fluorination level 5 one and NBR-10 fluorination level 9 sample owns the highest CoF among all three NBR #10 samples. Comparing with macroscopic friction data which higher fluorination level will lead to smaller friction, under microscopic scale, higher fluorination level will cause higher friction. This is probably due to that the fluorination is easily detached on NBR surface rather than FKM surface and higher fluorination level will cause more cleavages on the surface. More cleavages will lead higher micro line roughness when the contact area is extremely small.

3.2.2 Fluorination – Elevated Temperature at Fixed Sliding Velocity

Under different temperatures, rubber friction will change due to the viscoelastic behaviour of rubber materials. In this section, we will discuss how elevated temperature will affect the rubber friction in different fluorination level of rubber materials at a fixed sliding velocity (100 $\mu\text{m/s}$). The friction tests have been carried out at three specific temperatures which are 296 K, 323 K, and 373 K. As discussed above that fluorination process affects a lot in NBR #10 samples rather than FKM #2 and FKM #8 samples. Thus, we select NBR #10 as candidate material which is tested under different elevated temperatures and to observe whether the microscopic rubber friction behaviour at room temperature which we have already discussed at last chapter is the same as those at elevated temperature.

Figure 29: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 23 °C

Figure 30: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 50 °C

Figure 31: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 100 °C

From the graphs shown above, whether at room temperature (23 °C) or elevated temperature (50 °C and 100 °C), the coefficient of rubber friction increases with fluorination level which satisfied the conclusions we have drawn earlier in this chapter. Moreover, Schallamach waves (Schallamach, 1971) can be also observed at elevated temperatures which also verifies our previous results. Furthermore, we can observe that higher fluorination level will let the data become scattered. This is still caused by micro line roughness. We emphasize that in this chapter we only focus on the relationship of fluorination level and rubber friction, further information about how temperature will affect the frictional behaviour of rubber materials at the same fluorination level will be discussed later.

3.3 Sliding Velocity and Friction

As shown in the macroscopic friction test, sliding velocity will cause obvious effect of rubber friction coefficient. At microscopic scale, there are several factors affecting the friction. Sliding speed will also cause different in rubber friction. Thus, we select three different sliding velocities which are 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$, 100 $\mu\text{m/s}$ and 250 $\mu\text{m/s}$. Firstly, we carry out the test both on FKM material and NBR material in order to compare whether the sliding velocity will cause different frictional behaviours in both materials and which material will be affected more.

3.3.1 Sliding Velocity at Room Temperature - FKM

From the graphs listed below, we can find that at room temperature, lower speed will probably cause less scattered of the CoF vs Distance data. Moreover, we can find that at room temperature, there is no significant difference in rubber friction for FKM materials. This can be explained that in small scale, inertia will dominate the friction process during the tip-material interaction. Thus, little difference can be observed when the velocity is varied from 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ to 250 $\mu\text{m/s}$.

Figure 32: CoF vs Distance on FKM 10 $\mu\text{m/s}$ sliding velocity

Figure 33: CoF vs Distance on FKM 100 um/s sliding velocity

Figure 34: CoF vs Distance on FKM at 250 um/s sliding velocity

As shown in the above figures, Schallamach waves can be observed very clearly on no treated FKM samples. If we compare the CoF from different velocities, then plot a figure as below which can show a comparison of different velocity effects on FKM. From Figure 35, an overview graph, it indicates that there actually no obvious difference among different velocities. However, higher velocity probably leads to higher friction can be found detailed from the figure. As mentioned above, under microscopic scale, the sensitivity to the friction in NBR is higher than FKM both on pure polymer or fluorinated polymer surface.

Figure 35: CoF vs Distance on FKM under different velocities

3.3.2 Sliding Velocity at Room Temperature - NBR

From the figures listed below, it is demonstrated that at room temperature whether the sliding velocity is low or high, it has some difference on rubber friction in no treated NBR samples. Furthermore, as shown in these figures, at the same fluorination level, different velocity still affects the friction. The data is still scattered, and it is mainly due to the potential existing stick-slip phenomenon and Schallamach waves (Schallamach, 1953). This can satisfy the macroscopic friction results which also have the same phenomenon when sliding a bulk rubber sample on a metallic counter surface.

Figure 36: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 0.01 mm/s

Figure 37: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 0.1 mm/s

Figure 38: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 0.25 mm/s

Figure 39: Overview of fluorination, CoF and sliding velocity interactions for NBR #10

When comparing the difference of the velocity effect on the friction, we can plot an overview figure. Among no treated samples, we can find that the friction is smallest when the sliding velocity is also the minimum. Then with the increasing of sliding velocity, the friction increases as well. At no treated samples, when the sliding velocity reaches 0.25 mm/s, the rubber friction unexpectedly decreases. It is probably due to a manual mistake during the experiment, because we find that at other fluorinated samples, with the increasing of sliding velocity, the rubber friction continuously increases.

3.3.3 Sliding Velocity at Elevated Temperature – NBR

In order to simulate the real operation environment, elevated temperature test with different sliding velocities will be done as a part of this work. There should be coupling effect on

different velocities and temperatures (Gabriel, 2010). The experimental details can be found in the table below. We selected 50 °C and 100 °C as candidate temperature and under these temperatures, different sliding velocities from 0.01 mm/s to 0.25 mm/s will be done. At elevated temperature, in NBR #10 samples, we can find that higher velocity will still lead to higher friction and this satisfies the room temperature test.

Table B.8: Reference for experiments conducted with varying temperatures and sliding velocities			
Sample Name	Fluorination Level	Temperature	Velocity
NBR #10	0 (no treated)	23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C	0.01 mm/s, 0.1 mm/s, 0.25 mm/s
NBR #10	5	23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C	0.01 mm/s, 0.1 mm/s, 0.25 mm/s
NBR #10	9	23 °C, 50 °C, 100 °C	0.01 mm/s, 0.1 mm/s, 0.25 mm/s

Furthermore, whenever fluorination level is, higher velocity will still cause the higher friction. It provides the possibility that higher fluorination will let the friction higher in microscopic frictional behaviour and higher velocity will let the friction also higher in microscopic friction test.

Figure 40: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 50 °C and 0.01 mm/s

Figure 41: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 50 °C and 0.1 mm/s

Figure 42: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 50 °C and 0.25 mm/s

Figure 43: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 100 °C and 0.01 mm/s

Figure 44: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 100 °C and 0.1 mm/s

Figure 45: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 100 °C and 0.25 mm/s

Figure 46: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 50 °C at various velocities

Figure 47: CoF vs Fluorination Level on NBR #10 at 100 °C at various velocities

Figures shown above are a couple of different rubber friction versus sliding velocity at specific elevated temperature. From these figures, we can find that at the same fluorination level, rubber friction increases with the increasing of sliding velocity at both room temperature and elevated temperature.

3.4 Temperature and Friction

Aiming to clearer understand the frictional behaviour and the viscoelastic behaviour of candidate rubber materials, three specific temperatures which are 23 °C, 50 °C, and 100 °C are used coupling with a wide range of velocity.

3.4.1 Time-Temperature Superposition at Microscopic Scale

The figure below shows the time-temperature superposition for the rubber friction of NBR-10 specimen. Figure 48 shows the rubber friction coefficient versus log scale velocity. Then we plot a time-temperature master by using WLF equation (Grosch, 1963). Different curves of log velocity have been shifted to fit the curve. The data for NBR #10 no treated specimen is the most obvious phenomenon of time-temperature superposition. The reason is that no treated sample shows more viscoelastic behaviour.

Figure 48: CoF vs Sliding Velocity on NBR #10 no treated sample

Figure 49: Time-Temperature superposition master curve of the rubber friction coefficient at a reference 296 K temperature for NBR #10

From the time-temperature superposition master curve which is plotted by our data. Due to the viscoelastic behaviour of rubber sample which contact area which is governed by asperities of the rubber surface to the encountered surface keeps changing at different temperature, from high temperature to low temperature, rubber friction coefficient increases. However, from the literature and WLF equation, we can find that around T_g , the master curve will show a peak then it will decrease with decreasing of temperature. Thus, it seems under microscopic scale, time-temperature superposition still exists and it satisfies the macroscopic one, which may indicate that viscoelastic behaviour both revealed in bulk deformation or localised deformation.

3.5 Surface Hardness at Room Temperature

3.5.1 Equipment

Rubber surface hardness is traditionally and easily tested by shore hardness testing methodology. However, in order to obtain the microscopic surface hardness and well-known whether the rubber surface hardness will change with the viscoelastic behaviour or not. We use Agilent G200 Nano Indenter to carry out our experiment. The displacement is controlled by a capacitance gauge.

Figure 50: Agilent G200 Nano Indenter equipment

Figure 51: The schematic of indenter-sample interaction

3.5.2 Procedure

During nanoindentation process, the indenter moves towards the sample at a constant velocity. This is examined through a change in the stiffness response of the indenter by the controlled displacement or load. The load on the specimen can be shown:

$$P = \overbrace{(P_{raw} - P_0)}^{\text{Total Load}} - \overbrace{(h_{raw} - h_0)K_s}^{\text{Reaction Force of Support Springs}}$$

Then the displacement can be calculated by:

$$h_c = \overbrace{(h_{raw} - h_0)}^{\text{Total Tip Displacement}} - \overbrace{\frac{P_{raw} - P_0}{K_f}}^{\text{Frame Displacement}} - \overbrace{(t - t_0)Q}^{\text{Thermal Drift}}$$

The load-displacement data can be analyzed according to the Oliver and Pharr method. A typical load-displacement curve obtained from a nanoindentation test is shown in the figure below (Herbert, 2001).

Figure 52: Schematic of a nanoindentation induced material deformation and typical curve

Elastic modulus, E_r , is obtained by the calculation of the stiffness, S , of the initial part of the unloading curve. Moreover, the contact area between indenter and specimen surface is:

$$S = \frac{dP}{dh} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} E_r \sqrt{A}$$

Then if we arrange the former equation, we can obtain that,

$$E_r = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} S}{2 \sqrt{A}}$$

Then as we know from the hertz contact mechanism that modulus is,

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{E} + \frac{(1 - \nu_i^2)}{E_i}$$

Where the reduced modulus is combined with tip modulus and material modulus. Then the hardness can be expressed as,

$$H = \frac{P}{A}$$

3.5.3 Triaxial Creep during Surface Hardness Test

As we know that rubber material is viscoelastic, so the stress relaxation always take place during the mechanical test. That is the reason that modulus and hardness of a rubber material

is not fixed and can be changed with temperature and time. In this work, since the temperature and humidity in laboratory environment is constant, we can eliminate the majority of the effect in stress relaxation which is also can be represented as a triaxial creep during the test. Thus, we assume that the longer peak load time will lead to more accurate hardness.

Figure 53: 10 seconds peak load hold time load-displacement curve

Figure 54: 100 seconds peak load hold time load-displacement curve

Figure 55: 1000 seconds peak load hold time load-displacement curve

Figure 56: 10000 seconds peak load hold time load-displacement curve

As shown from the figures, we can find that each curve represents an indent and the data is not reproducible. It is due to each indent locates on different surface region, so the mechanical properties for each indent are different. Moreover, it indicates that viscoelastic behaviour of rubber material will dominate the unloading process. We have to let the rubber specimen take some time to stress relax, otherwise, the initial portion of the unloading curve is incorrect and the stiffness obtained from this kind of curve is negative number which is undeniably incorrect. Then we assume longer peak load holding time during the nanoindentation process will lead to fuller stress relaxation and it will help to obtain a more correct curve. In this case, we have tried 10s, 100s, 1000s, and 10000s peak load hold time in order to research the triaxial creep during the nanoindentation test. All these efforts are aiming to obtain a comparable correct surface hardness. If we select the peak load hold time versus the displacement, then we can get an overall figure. Noted, nanoindentation test is a triaxial stress state test, which is different from cantilever and uniaxial tension test.

Figure 57: Triaxial creep curve (Time vs Displacement) on FKM

From the creep curve, we can find that longer time will lead to stable displacement changing. Therefore, we assume that longer peak load hold time will lead to a more correct surface hardness value.

3.5.4 Surface Hardness – Micro Scale

As mentioned above, microscopic stress relaxation is similar as the conventional stress relaxation measurement which is always known as weaker polymer-filler interaction the greater relaxation can be observed and no significant difference will be observed between pure rubbers. In this case, we choose filled FKM as candidate materials and we use the equations which are listed above to fit the unloading portion of the load displacement data with the Oliver and Pharr power-law relation. Then we can obtain the reduced modulus from the stiffness and the contact area which is calculated by already known indenter geometry.

Figure 58: Surface hardness versus peak load hold time on FKM

From the figure shown above, a decrease in hardness with peak load hold time can be observed. Briefly, shorter peak load hold time will lead to higher surface hardness. Then we will say that for viscoelastic material, a peak load hold time has to be applied at the maximum indentation loading, otherwise the surface hardness is not accurate. In this work, at 10 s peak load hold time, the surface hardness is approximately 7 MPa and at 10000 s peak load hold time, the surface hardness is about 1 MPa. So it is indicated that 10000 times longer of the peak load hold time will let the surface hardness decrease about 7 times. The reason behind this can also be explained by viscoelastic behaviour in filled rubber material. Moreover, the issues are non-uniform filler distribution will affect all mechanical properties at microscopic scale. From the above chapters, we can find that both rubber friction and surface hardness will be easily affected by topography and morphology of the rubber surface and the filler distribution. So, in the next chapter we will research the microscopies which are applied onto rubber surface and

we can compare whether the surface roughness or surface conditions will affect the results largely.

4. MATLAB Coding (SL)

In this work, we use nano indenter as our main tool to obtain different microscopic mechanical properties. So how to analyse raw data from equipment and get the useful mechanical data is very essential. So, a MATLAB code is programmed in this work to smartly analyse different engineering materials. It is likely that this MATLAB code can be run on general PC (Windows or Linux). MAC OS version have been tested by developers that currently can not be used. Ideally, this MATLAB code can be run on the platform version 6.0 or above. For the current stage, it is unable to read the files directly from Agilent nano indenter G200 experiment software (NanoSuite). Ideally, we can export the nanoindentation test data into excel format firstly. Then we can import the excel into our MATLAB. The following is to be read: beginning with the left-hand column, reading downwards until end of page, then beginning of right hand column.

4.1 Stress-Strain Data Analysis

```
% Copy right: Shibai Liao
```

```
clear all;
```

```
close all;
```

```
% Discretisation parameters:
```

```
X_axis=0:0.005:0.2;
```

```
Color = rand(5,3);
```

```
Color2=rand(5,3);
```

```
Shape={'+', 'o', '*', 's', 'd', 'v', '.'};
```

```
%Define the final outcomes
```

```
Stress_norm=zeros(200,41); % Creating  
stress variable for all indents
```

```
Var_total=zeros(20,41); % Creating stress  
variable for all indents
```

```
Mean_total=zeros(20,41); % Mean Stress  
after interpolation
```

```
Norm_Dia=zeros(2,401); % upper boundary  
of elastic region for each indent (user  
selected)
```

```
Mean_Dia=zeros(2,41); % average 'yield  
stress' as selected by the user
```

```
std_Dia=zeros(1,41);
```

```

legend_s={'1','2','3','4','5','6','7','8','9','10','11','
12','13','14','15','16','17','18','19','20'};
%
excel_num=0;
data_num=0;
while(1)
disp('Please input the name of the Excel file.
Input 0 when complete');
u1=input('s');
if(u1=='0')
break;
end

excel_num=excel_num+1;
legend_s{1,excel_num}=u1; % name of data
series
num_d=cell2mat(regex(u1,'\d','match')); %
create excel file name as non case sensitive
Exl_Dia{1,excel_num}=num_d; % Matrix of
excel file names
%Select up to 36 indents
Stress=zeros(36,41);
Stress_std=zeros(36,41);
name=strcat(u1,'.xls');
disp('Please input the column name');
l1=input('Input the y axis excel column
name\n','s');
l2=input('Input the x axis excel column
name\n','s');
%Simplify the reading process
[~,~,stress_all]=xlsread(name,1,strcat(l1,num
2str(1),':',l1,num2str(2000)));
[~,~,strain_all]=xlsread(name,1,strcat(l2,num
2str(1),':',l2,num2str(2000)));

```

```

disp('Please input the number of indents');
num=input('number of indents\n');

for i=1:num
% Define row bounds for each indent
a=input(strcat('Number ',num2str(i),' indent
starting row\n'));
b=input(strcat('Number ',num2str(i),' indent
ending row\n'));
temp_stress=stress_all(a:b);
temp_strain=strain_all(a:b);
len=length(temp_stress);
A=zeros(1,len);
% remove NaN
for j=1:len
if(isnan(temp_stress{j,1})|isnan(temp_strain{
j,1}))
A(1,j)=1;
end
end
temp_stress(A~=0)=[];
temp_strain(A~=0)=[];

% remove strings
len=length(temp_stress);
A=zeros(1,len);
for j=1:len
if(ischar(temp_stress{j,1})|ischar((temp_strai
n{j,1})))
A(1,j)=1;
end
end
temp_stress(A~=0)=[];

```

```

temp_strain(A~=0)=[];
% change data type from cells to matrix
temp_stress=cell2mat(temp_stress);
temp_strain=cell2mat(temp_strain);
% transpose matrix to horizontal
temp_stress=[0;temp_stress];
temp_strain=[0;temp_strain];
temp=[temp_strain temp_stress];
% Sort data for strain in ascending order
temp=sortrows(temp,1);
temp_strain=temp(:,1);
temp_stress=temp(:,2);

figure();
plot(temp_strain,temp_stress,'!');
hold on;
%Select the lower boundry
[x1,y1]=ginput(1);
plot(x1,y1,'r*');
hold on;
%Select the upper boundry
[x2,y2]=ginput(1);
plot(x2,y2,'r*');
hold on;
%Remove low load noise
temp2_strain=temp_strain(temp_stress>y1);
temp2_stress=temp_stress(temp_stress>y1);
% Linear fitting
if(x1==x2)
k(i)=0;
else
k(i)=(y2-y1)/(x2-x1);
end
%Extend the line to the x-axis
b=y2-x2*k(i); % y intercept
X_node=-b/k(i); % x intercept
line([X_node,x2],[0,y2],'color','r');
%Shift to the origin
temp2_strain=temp2_strain+X_node;
temp2_strain=[0;temp2_strain];
temp2_stress=[0;temp2_stress];

%Linear interpolation
Stress(i,:)=interp1(temp2_strain,temp2_stress
,X_axis, 'linear');
data_num=data_num+1;
%Save the data after interpolation
Norm_Dia(1,data_num)=i;
Norm_Dia(2,data_num)=y2;

Stress_norm(data_num,:)=Stress(i,:);
end
Mean_Dia(1,excel_num)= mean(tempy2);
std_Dia(1,excel_num)=std(tempy2);
Stress=Stress([1:num],:);
Stress_var=stdev(Stress);
Stress_mean=mean(Stress);
Mean_Dia(1,excel_num)= mean(tempy2);
std_Dia(1,excel_num)=std(tempy2);
Mean_total(excel_num,:)=Stress_mean;%Sa
ve all the mean stress data after the
interpolation
% Figure with an errobar
figure();

```

```

errorbar(X_axis,Stress_mean,Stress_var,Shape{1,mod(excel_num,7)+1},'color',Color(mod(excel_num,5)+1,:),'linewidth',1.5);

xlabel('Strain(a/R)','FontSize',15);
ylabel('Stress (GPa)','FontSize',15);

title('Size Effect Post Cu.xlsx/n Stress VS Strain','FontSize',15);

legend(u1);

end

%Come out the former for loop and plot the overall figure
figure();

for i=1:excel_num
errorbar(X_axis,Mean_total(i,:),Var_total(i,:),Shape{1,mod(i,7)+1},'color',Color(mod(i,5)+1,:),'linewidth',1.5);

hold on;

end

```

```

xlabel('Strain(a/R)','FontSize',15);
ylabel('Stress (GPa)','FontSize',15);

title('Size Effect Cu Singlecrystal Stress VS Strain','FontSize',15);

legend(legend_s);

% %Plot the elastic limit graph
figure();

errorbar(1:excel_num,Mean_Dia(1:excel_num),std_Dia(1:excel_num),'*',color,'r','linewidth',1.5);

set(gca,'XTick',1:excel_num);

set(gca,'XTickLabel',Exl_Dia);

xlabel('Tip Radius(um)','FontSize',15);

ylabel('Elastic Limit (GPa)','FontSize',15);

title('Size Effect','FontSize',15);

```

4.2 Modulus/Hardness-Strain Data Analysis

```
%Copy right: Shibai Liao
```

```
clear all;
```

```
close all;
```

```
%Define abscissa
```

```
X_axis=0:0.005:0.2;
```

```
%Define random shape and color
```

```
Color = rand(5,3);
```

```
Color2=rand(5,3);
```

```
Shape={'+', 'o', '*', 's', 'd', 'v', '.'};
```

```
Stress_norm=zeros(200,41);
```

```
Var_total=zeros(20,41);
```

```
Mean_total=zeros(20,41);
```

```
legend_s={'1','2','3','4','5','6','7','8','9','10','11','12','13','14','15','16','17','18','19','20'};
```

```
excel_num=0;
```

```
data_num=0;
```

```
while(1)
```

```
disp('Please input name of the Excel file, 0 as the end');
```

```
u1=input('','s');
```

```
if(u1=='0')
```

```
break;
```

```
end
```

```

excel_num=excel_num+1;
legend_s{1,excel_num}=u1;
%Maximum select 9 indents in one time
Stress=zeros(9,41);
Stress_std=zeros(1,41);
name=strcat(u1,'.xls');
disp('Please input the column name');
l1=input('Input the first column\n','s');
l2=input('Input the second column\n','s');
%Simplify all the reading process

[~,~,stress_all]=xlsread(name,1,strcat(l1,num
2str(1),':',l1,num2str(1000)));

[~,~,strain_all]=xlsread(name,1,strcat(l2,num
2str(1),':',l2,num2str(1000)));

disp('Please input the number of indents');
num=input('umber of indents\n');

for i=1:num

a=input(strcat('Number',num2str(i),'indent's
starting row\n'));

b=input(strcat('Number',num2str(i),'indent's
ending row\n'));

temp_stress=stress_all(a:b);
temp_strain=strain_all(a:b);
len=length(temp_stress);
A=zeros(1,len);
for j=1:len

if(isnan(temp_stress{j,1})|isnan(temp_strain{
j,1}))

A(1,j)=1;

end

end

temp_stress(A~=0)=[];
temp_strain(A~=0)=[];

len=length(temp_stress);
A=zeros(1,len);
for j=1:len

if(ischar(temp_stress{j,1})|ischar((temp_strai
n{j,1})))

A(1,j)=1;

end

end

temp_stress(A~=0)=[];
temp_strain(A~=0)=[];
temp_stress=cell2mat(temp_stress);
temp_strain=cell2mat(temp_strain);
temp_stress=[0;temp_stress];
temp_strain=[0;temp_strain];
temp=[temp_strain temp_stress];
temp=sortrows(temp,1);
temp_strain=temp(:,1);
temp_stress=temp(:,2);

Stress(i,:)=interp1(temp_strain,temp_stress,X
_axis, 'linear');

data_num=data_num+1;

Stress_norm(data_num,:)=Stress(i,:);

end

end

Stress=Stress([1:num],:);
Stress_var=var(Stress);
Stress_mean=mean(Stress);

```

```

Var_total(excel_num,:)=Stress_var;
Mean_total(excel_num,:)=Stress_mean;
figure();
errorbar(X_axis,Stress_mean,Stress_var,Shape{1,mod(excel_num,7)+1},'color',Color(mod(excel_num,5)+1,:),'linewidth',1.5);
xlabel('Strain(a/R)','FontSize',15);
title('Size Effect Post Cu.xlsx/n Stress VS Strain','FontSize',15);
legend(u1);
end

```

```

figure();
for i=1:excel_num
errorbar(X_axis,Mean_total(i,:),Var_total(i,:),Shape{1,mod(i,7)+1},'color',Color(mod(i,5)+1,:),'linewidth',1.5);
hold on;
end
xlabel('Strain(a/R)','FontSize',15);
title('Size Effect Post Cu.xlsx/n Stress VS Strain','FontSize',15);
legend(legend_s);

```

4.3 Contact Area Calibration from Tip Radius

```

% Copy right: Shibai Liao
% SPHEREFIT find least squares sphere
% Fit a sphere to a set of xyz data points
% [center,radius,residuals] = shperefit(X)
% [center,radius,residuals] =
spherefit(x,y,z);
% Input
% x,y,z Cartesian data, n x 3 matrix or
three vectors (n x 1 or 1 x n)
% Output
% center least squares sphere center
coordinates, == [xc yc zc]
% radius radius of curvature
% residuals residuals in the radial direction
% Fit the equation of a sphere in Cartesian
coordinates to a set of xyz
% data points by solving the
overdetermined system of normal
equations,ie,  $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + a*x + b*y + c*z + d = 0$ 
% The least squares sphere has radius  $R = \sqrt{(a^2+b^2+c^2)/4-d}$  and

```

```

% center coordinates (x,y,z) = (-a/2,-b/2,-c/2)
n=1;
l=1;
Results=zeros(50,2);
while n==1,
%import data from ASSIC file
A=uiimport('-file');
data = getfield(A,'data');
%convert data to format with dimension:
m x 3
k=1;
X=zeros(801*801,3);
for i=112:912
m=112;
for j=112:912
X(k,1)=data(i,1);

```

```

        X(k,2)=data(m,1);
        X(k,3)=data(i,j+1);
        k=k+1; m=m+1;
    end
end

% save columns as x,y,z vectors
z = X(:,3);
y = X(:,2);
x = X(:,1);

% solve linear system of normal equations
A = [x y z ones(size(x))];
b = -(x.^2 + y.^2 + z.^2);
a = A \ b;

% return center coordinates and sphere
radius
center = -a(1:3)./2;

% the a sphere with center (x0, y0, z0) and
radius R can be described as (x-x0)^2+(y-
y0)^2+(z-z0)^2=R^2
radius = sqrt(sum(center.^2)-a(4));

% calculate residuals (calculated R minus
distance between center and each point)
residuals = radius -
sqrt(sum(bsxfun(@minus,[x y
z],center).^2,2));
averesiduals=mean(residuals);
residualsplot = zeros(801,801);

% calculate residuals (calculated z minus
real z values)
residuals1=zeros(size(residuals));
for i=1:641601
residuals1(i)=(sqrt(radius^2-(x(i)-
center(1))^2-(y(i)-
center(2))^2)+center(3))-z(i);
end
plot3(x(1:1:641601)-27.75,y(1:1:641601)-
27.75,residuals1(1:1:641601),'.','MarkerSiz
e',0.05);

k=1;
for i=1:801
    for j=1:801
        residualsplot(i,j)=residuals(k,1);
        k=k+1;
    end
end

%loop for next data set

%Plot 3-D data
ellipsoid(center(1,1)-27.75,center(2,1)-
27.75,center(3,1), radius,radius,radius);

hold on
plot3(x(1:10:641601)-
27.75,y(1:10:641601)-
27.75,z(1:10:641601),'.','MarkerSize',0.05)
;
Results(1,1)=radius;
Results(1,2)=averesiduals;

n=input('Do you want to do another plot:
');
if isempty(n);

```

```

n=1;                                end
elseif n=='y';
    n=1;
else n=0;                            k=1;
end %if                               for i=1:801
l=l+1;                                plot3(x((801*(k-1)+1):10:(801*(k-
end% while                            1)+801),1),y((801*(k-1)+1):10:(801*(k-
                                        1)+801),1),residualsplot(i,1:10:801),'.', 'Ma
                                        rkerSize',0.05)

k=1; for i=1:801                       k=k+1; hold on
    plot3(x((801*(k-1)+1):(801*(k-    end
    1)+801),1),y((801*(k-1)+1):(801*(k-
    1)+801),1),residualsplot(i,:))
    k=k+1; hold on

```

5. Materials Characterisation (AA & SL)

Comprehensive characterisation of the fluorinated and non-fluorinated NBR and FKM elastomers is vital to understanding how the surface treatment affects their subsequent properties. This section will present the information gathered from their usage.

5.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (AA)

An invaluable tool in determining the chemical composition of a material through identification of specific functional groups, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) enables, firstly, confirmation of a successful surface treatment. This feature constitutes an important piece of information regarding the process, indicating efficiency and effectiveness.

Figure 59: FTIR spectra of FKM #2 – Level 0 and Level 9

Wavenumber (cm⁻¹)	Functional Group
1405	F-CH ₂
1274	CF
1234	CF ₂ and CF
887	CF ₃

Figures 59, 60, 61 and 62 display the FTIR spectra for the three samples, with Tables B.9, B.10, B.11 and B.12 listing the identified functional groups. The characteristic peaks of 887 cm⁻¹, 1274 cm⁻¹ and 1405 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the groups CF₃, CF and F-CH₂ respectively, are visible for FKM #2 in Figure 59, and there is negligible difference between the obtained spectra for Level 0 and Level 9. For FKM #8, shown in Figure 60, Levels 0 and 5, the identifiable functional groups represent the known features of fluoroelastomers, as FKM #2, with some

additional features: 2969 cm^{-1} , 1450 cm^{-1} and 1040 cm^{-1} , reflecting CH_2 , CH and $\text{CH}_2\text{-C}$ groups respectively.

Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional Group
2969	CH_2 and CH
1699 (<i>Level 5</i>)	$\text{C}=\text{O}$
1450	$\text{CH}_2\text{-C}$
1143	CF_2
1040	CF_2
784	CF_3
550	

Figure 60: FTIR spectra of FKM #8 - Level 0 and Level 5

Figures 60 and 61, along with Tables B.11 and B.12 present the spectra obtained for the NBR samples. NBR Level 0 displays a strongly characteristic shape, with the peaks of 2227 cm^{-1} and 954 cm^{-1} corresponding to the functional nitrile and butadiene groups respectively. Also visible is the decreasing NBR character of each sample as fluorination occurs, with some of the emblematic peaks beginning to subside, and new ones suggesting the introduction of new

functional groups as a result of the surface treatment; most salient of these emerging peaks being at 1731 cm^{-1} and 1125 cm^{-1} . As shown in Table B.11, the identified functional groups are C=O and C-F, demonstrating the successful application of a surface treatment. Figure 61 further illustrates the changes occurring during the fluorination process, as the original NBR profile has largely faded away, though some of the archetypal features have remained faintly visible. The newly identified peaks have persisted in the spectra obtained for NBR Level 9, with the shoulder at 1409 cm^{-1} increasing in prominence, representing $\text{CF}_3\text{-CF}_2$ groups as the enhanced level of fluorinated causes further fluorine attachment on the elastomer surface.

Table B.11: FTIR spectra of NBR L0 and L5	
Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional Group
2908 - 2834	CH_2, CH
2227	$\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$
1731 (<i>Level 5</i>)	C=O
1423 (<i>Level 0</i>)	$\text{CH}_2\text{-C}$
1125 (<i>Level 5</i>)	C-F
1097 (<i>Level 5</i>)	C-O
954	$\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$

Table B.12: FTIR spectra of NBR L9	
Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional Group
2319	$\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$
1747	C=O
1604	
1409	$\text{CF}_3\text{-CF}_2$
1143	C-F
943	$\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$

Figure 62: FTIR spectra of NBR samples - Level 0 and Level 5 fluorination

Figure 61: FTIR spectra for NBR Level 9 fluorination

5.2 Contact Angle Measurements (AA)

Contact angle measurements were made using a Kruss 100 Drop Shape Analyser, employing the sessile drop technique. A droplet of the probe liquid is created at the syringe needle tip, which is then brought into contact with the sample surface and deposited. A high-resolution camera captures an image of the droplet on the surface and image analysis software is used to determine the contact angle. Three separate locations on each sample were analysed in this

manner, with averages taken. The probe liquids were de-ionised water and ethylene glycol, with an additional three mixtures made to dilutions of 25 % ethylene glycol/75 % de-ionised water, 50 % ethylene glycol/50 % de-ionised water and 75 % ethylene glycol/25 % de-ionised water.

Surface energy manifests its influence through a variety of phenomena, both mechanical and chemical, making it imperative to track and understand the impact fluorination has on the surface energy. By plotting the surface tension of the probe liquid against the cosine of its measured contact angle, extrapolation of this construction to the point where $\cos(\theta) = 1$ yields the critical surface tension, the surface tension of the liquid completely wetting the solid surface, which according to Zisman theory, equates to the solid surface energy. Unlike the one-component Zisman theory, Owens-Wendt theory considers the separate contributions to surface energy from both dispersive and polar interactions, by modifying both the Young-Dupré and Goods-Girifalco-Fowkes equations, producing a relationship specifying each contribution. The three component van Oss theory further divides the polar component upon acidic and basic interactions, with this theory being more suited for organometallics. The nature of the elastomers under investigation meant that both Zisman and Owens-Wendt theory were used to determine their surface energies.

Table B.13: Calculated Surface Energies of Samples			
	Fluorination Level	Surface Energy (mJ.m⁻²)	
		Zisman	Owens-Wendt
NBR	L0	N/A	11.79
	L5	30	34.75
	L9	7.5	19.2
FKM #8	L0	9.5	N/A
	L5	17	18.96
	L9	N/A	24.5
FKM #2	L0	7	14.92
	L9	N/A	20.72

Table B.14: Contact Angles for Selected Probe Liquids on Samples				
		θ (°)		
		H₂O	50 % EG/ 50% H₂O	Ethylene Glycol
NBR	L0	111.1	95.41	81
	L5	80.78	60.89	52.81
	L9	90.58	79.61	66.87
FKM #8	L0	120.12	98.30	84.26
	L5	89.35	87.47	62.99
	L9	92.3	86.84	75.44
FKM #2	L0	105.69	90.65	73.89
	L9	90.87	78.8	68.17

Fluorination of the NBR, from Level 0 to Level 5, increased its hydrophilicity as seen by the decrease in contact angles measured, 111.1 ° to 80.78 °, with a subsequent increase (90.58 °) from Level 5 to Level 9. This is reflected in the reported surface energy of each sample, as it increases from 11.79 mJ.m⁻², to 37.75 mJ.m⁻² and then decreases to 19.2 mJ.m⁻². The same occurs for FKM #8, with the contact angles decreasing from Level 0 to Level 5, and then increasing again at Level 9; nevertheless, the surface energy measured continues to increase, although slightly, from Level 5 to Level 9, unlike the decrease of NBR. FKM #2 displays the same trend, as fluorination from Level 0 to Level 9 has decreased the hydrophobicity, yielding measurement of smaller contact angles, with an increase in the surface energy from 14.92 mJ.m⁻² to 20.72 mJ.m⁻².

As mentioned, the surface treatment of NBR is apparent from the FTIR results as the varying peaks reflect on the changing nature of the functional groups present on the surface for each sample. Appearing at both levels 5 and 9, important peaks include those at 1125 cm⁻¹, 1143 cm⁻¹ and 1409 cm⁻¹, denoting C-F, C-F and CF₃-CF₂ groups respectively. Interestingly, peaks again absent for NBR Level 0, yet visible for levels 5 and 9 include 1097 cm⁻¹, 1731 cm⁻¹ and 1743 cm⁻¹ have been identified as representing C-O and C=O groups; this may suggest a possible oxy-fluorination technique has been applied to these samples, resulting in the formation of these emblematic bonds. Furthermore, a similar feature is seen in Figure 60, illustrating the spectra for FKM #8, with the peak at 1699 cm⁻¹ again indicating a C=O group and oxy-fluorination, or the inclusion of oxygen during the process, whether intentionally or inadvertently. Though typically reported that fluorination leads to an increase in hydrophobicity and simultaneous decrease in surface tension, the reverse here observed,

namely the increased surface energy and gradual increase in hydrophilicity may be attributed to the presence of oxygen in the original surface treatment. The presence of oxygen induces the formation of polar oxygen containing groups during the treatment, significantly affecting the resulting properties of the material as oxidation of the elastomer surface occurs, increasing the surface energy of the elastomers. The relative decrease in surface energy observed for NBR from Level 5 to Level 9 may be explained by reference to the nature of the fluorination process. A radical chain process, the duration of time permitted for such a reaction to continue has a direct bearing on the outcomes, with the increased duration of Level 9, relative to Level 5, ensuring that the extremely polar oxygen containing groups formed prior to that point in the process had now been replaced with an increased amount of fluorine containing groups. Analysis of Figures 62 and 63 elucidate that the peak at 1097 cm^{-1} , present in Figure 62, is no longer salient in Figure 63, and the appearance of the more prominent shoulder at 1409 suggests the replacement of the C-O group with $\text{CF}_3\text{-CF}_2$ groups as the fluorination technique has continued from Level 5 to Level 9. The persistence of C=O groups, specified by the 1747 cm^{-1} peak may be due to the difficulty in removing a double bond.

The changes in surface energy determined through contact angle measurements, coupled with the observations of an evolving chemical composition obtained through FTIR results, serve to demonstrate the influence fluorination has on these elastomers. The treatment introduces polar oxygen containing groups onto the surface, significantly affecting the resulting properties of the material. Nevertheless, the process also introduces fluorine and related fluorine groups, a strongly electronegative element, with these two consolidating each other it seems.

5.3 Microscopy (SL)

5.3.1 Confocal Microscopy

As mentioned in previous chapter, microscopic friction in rubber material is mainly due to the surface roughness. There are several methods to characterise topography and morphology of rubber surface, such as AFM, SEM and Confocal Microscope. In this work, confocal microscope and SEM will be used to analyse the surface. Confocal Microscopy is a kind of microscope which can both two dimensional and three dimensional scan the surface of the object. The main principle is that the laser will scan at different focal plane, and combine all of

the focal plane and pixels to make a three-dimensional image which can be applied to different software.

Figure 63: Surface morphology of FKM #2 no treated specimen

Figure 64: 3D Surface topography of FKM #2 no treated specimen

Figure 65: 2D Surface topography of FKM #2 no treated specimen

Figure 66: Surface morphology of FKM #2 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 67: 3D Surface topography of FKM #2 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 68: 2D Surface topography of FKM #2 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 69: Surface morphology of FKM #8 no treated specimen

Figure 70: 3D Surface topography of FKM #8 no treated specimen

Figure 71: 2D Surface topography of FKM #8 no treated specimen

Figure 72: Surface morphology of FKM #8 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 73: 3D Surface topography of FKM #8 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 74: 2D Surface topography of FKM #8 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 75: Surface morphology of FKM #8 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 76: 3D Surface topography of FKM #8 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 77: 2D Surface topography of FKM #8 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 78: Surface morphology of NBR #10 no treated specimen

Figure 79: 3D Surface topography of NBR #10 no treated specimen

Figure 80: 2D Surface topography of NBR #10 no treated specimen

Figure 81: Surface morphology of NBR #10 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 82: 3D Surface topography of NBR #10 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 83: 2D Surface topography of NBR #10 fluorination level 5 specimen

Figure 84: Surface morphology of NBR #10 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 85: 3D Surface topography of NBR #10 fluorination level 9 specimen

Figure 86: 2D Surface topography of NBR #10 fluorination level 9 specimen

As shown from these confocal microscope images, we can find that higher fluorination will lead to a larger line roughness. This is due to higher fluorination also will cause cleavages, cracks and fractures on rubber surface. The micro line roughness can be examined in the table below.

Table B.14: Micro Line Roughness of each Specimen		
Sample Name	Ra (ISO4287) (um)	Rz (ISO4287) (um)
FKM #2-level 0	0.043	0.400
FKM #2-level 9	0.044	0.380
FKM #8-level 0	0.021	0.023
FKM #8-level 5	0.023	0.151
FKM #8-level 9	0.042	0.425
NBR #10-level 0	0.016	0.103
NBR #10-level 5	0.056	0.439
NBR #10-level 9	0.065	0.445

These line roughness results satisfy the frictional results of the rubber samples. As discussed in the previous chapter, higher fluorination will lead to higher microscopic friction which is opposite to the macro bulk friction. Then the results obtained by confocal microscope show that higher fluorination will lead to higher line roughness. As we know, micro friction is a kind of localised deformation which line roughness is very essential to the rubber friction coefficient. Moreover, through three-dimensional image, we can find that there is an orientation on the rubber surface. This is probably due to the manufacturing process causing the orientation on the rubber surface.

5.3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is a kind of imaging technique which uses high-energy beam of electrons to raster scan the sample surface. Since the rubber is not very conductive, so usually we coat rubber by gold or carbon to let it more conductive. In this work, we use this kind of technique to research the filler distribution in the filled rubber and to see whether the polymer-filler interaction will affect the surface hardness as we assumed in former chapter.

Figure 87: Surface morphology of FKM samples

Figure 88: Surface morphology of FKM samples at higher magnification

From these two SEM images, we can find that the filler distribution is not very uniform in all the selected regions. This verifies that why the surface hardness is different. Under 50 μm magnification, we can find that some of fillers are larger than the tip radius (25 μm) we use. If the indenter hit the filler, polymer, or filler-polymer interaction region, the surface hardness

value is very different. This can also explain the different results obtained by various repeats of microscopic friction, when the indenter is sliding through different regions of rubber surface. Thus, we draw the conclusion that at microscopic scale, filler distribution will cause different line roughness. Different line roughness will result in different micro friction. Higher level of fluorination means longer time immersion in F_2 gas and it will cause the severe increase of line surface roughness at small scale. So from our works, at higher level of fluorination, the sample behaves a higher friction at micro scale. Furthermore, we can also assume that higher fluorination will lead to higher surface hardness, and it can be verified in the future works. Temperature and humidity will also affect the micro test, since the indenter penetration depth is nano meter scale, so the water film or very little thermal expansion will make the final results show error. In order to eliminate the external effects which will cause different results, a constant lab environment is needed.

6. Discussion & Conclusions

The investigation has revealed a number of salient features pertinent to the application of fluorination to those elastomers intended for use as seals in the oil and gas industry. This work will study these points as they relate to the outlined project aims, enabling a comprehensive account of the investigation and project. Important insights into the influence fluorination has on the examined elastomers points to the ability to successfully apply the surface treatment, its impact on the observed frictional behaviours, at both macro and micro scale, and the adequacy of the constructed macro friction test rig in measuring the coefficient of friction values.

Foremost amongst the findings of the investigation is the increased susceptibility of NBR to fluorination relative to FKM. Comparison of Figures 59 through to Figure 62 elucidate this, as the NBR character is affected strongly at each level of fluorination, beginning with Figure 62, a graph typical of NBR, proceeding to Figure 61, displaying, or rather, lacking in the emblematic peaks of NBR, and displaying those peaks, as mentioned in Section 5, indicative of fluorine group attachment to a material surface. Though Figure 60 demonstrates some modification to the FKM #8 specimen following fluorination, the changes visible are far greater for the NBR specimen, with the pre-existing fluoroelastomer nature of FKM ensuring further changes are none too visible on an FTIR spectrum, though, the investigation has shown that the changes induced by fluorination can be measured through other techniques, namely measurement of mechanical behaviour, to be discussed. The presence of the more readily accessible butadiene group in NBR permits the enhanced attachment of fluorine groups as opposed to the saturated fluorine nature of FKM. This difference in the extent of modification is corroborated by the statistical analysis of the coefficient of friction (CoF) values obtained through the macro friction testing, specifically the observed percentage changes for each material. Displaying average CoF changes of 26.5 % and 27.5 % respectively, FKM #2 and FKM #8 are far below the observed average CoF change of 78 % for NBR #10, demonstrating this increased susceptibility of NBR to fluorination. The micro friction testing of chapter 3 also provides data furthering this point, as Figures 21 to Figure 25 illustrate the similar CoF values obtained for both FKM specimens, as opposed to Figures 26, 27 and 28, which show the changing CoF of 0.17 for NBR #10 Level 0, the 0.2 for NBR #10 Level 5 and 0.25 for NBR #10 Level 9.

Extraction of CoF values from both the micro and macro friction tests and subsequent comparison has revealed an ostensible disparity between the two sets of data, namely, the increasing of the CoF with fluorination as observed at the micro scale, and the decrease of the CoF with fluorination as observed at the macro scale; though this can be reconciled with the recognition that fluorination is a surface treatment. It is known that fluorination can cause cracking at the surface of a material as uneven shrinkage of the separate components occurs due to differences in their density (Kramer et al., 2011). The increase prevalence of these cleavages along the surface may become more apparent at the micro scale, as they begin to impose themselves, greatly increasing the friction between the measuring instrument and specimen. Moreover, agitation of these asperities by an instrument such as that used in the micro-scale test may induce thermal local effects (Verheyde et al., 2009) increasing the CoF, as known through visco-elastic theory. The increasing of temperature is akin to lowering the modulus of these filled elastomer, due to the weakening of filler interactions through interface slippage. A decrease in modulus, or increase in temperature, leads to increased viscosity and hence higher CoF as observed in the micro friction test. Conversely, at the macro scale, the decrease in friction with fluorination, relative to non-fluorinated samples, can be attributed to the formation of a thin transfer film, essentially lubricating the surfaces in contact (Verheyde et al., 2009 & Huang, 2014), reducing the CoF of the elastomer as it slides along the aluminium counterface. This is amplified by the varying contact areas under examination in both tests, as the micro test exacerbates the effects of these local surface cracks, whilst the macro test permits, firstly, the inclusion of contamination layer effects. The presence of these contaminants dampens the potential energy dissipations from the various cavities and asperities of the surface, reducing the CoF measured (Persson, 2001). As explained, this is not the case at the micro level as local effects are amplified in that situation. Moreover, the inducement of cross-linking by fluorination, whether by thermal activation or addition of radical species, increases the hardness and modulus of the surface of the material (Vega-Cantu et al., 2002), decreasing friction as explained by visco-elastic theory. The observance of decreased friction with higher sliding velocities fits this theory as again, increasing speed denies the polymer chains the chance to respond to an applied external stress, transferring them into a glassy state, reducing the friction. Thus, it is implied that fluorination of an elastomer and subsequent measurement of said materials frictional behaviour is highly dependent the scale at which this phenomenon is measured.

Another important observation made in macro friction investigation is that for both FKM #8 and NBR #10, the CoF, having decreased from Level 0 to Level 5 fluorination, increases again at Level 9, relative to Level 5. A higher level of fluorination may excessively etch away loose particles from the surface, resulting in an extremely clean surface, free of the contamination layer alluded to earlier. Furthermore, the increased intensity of the surface treatment leads to fundamental changes in the nature of the bonds present, as illustrated in the FTIR spectra displayed and the surface energies calculated through contact angle measurements. The polar groups introduced enable enhanced adhesion to the aluminium surface, accounting for the increased CoF values for FKM #8 and NBR #10.

7. Future Work & Development (NM)

With regards to the friction results, especially for macro scale friction test, a number of improvements for the friction test rig, experimental procedure, and also possible avenues to further the research can be executed in future work, these are listed in this section.

- Further experimental work attempting to improve the mechanical compliance and losses of the friction test rig should be attempted. The evaluation of the friction rig undertaken in Chapter 2, it was noted the two bearings contributed to a 1.7% increase in the load reading when the wire was put under tension under a 1kg deadweight. A detailed bearing selection may enable to reduce this load contribution, thus reducing experimental error.
- While our work has identified the influence fluorination and sliding velocity has onto the coefficient of friction, it has not related the contribution of temperature. The friction rig manufactured in this study is fully compatible with Instron environmental chambers, therefore further experimental work can be undertaken to quantify the relationship with temperature.
- The coefficient of friction is a function of both the elastomer and substrate. Although the elastomer surface was varied through fluorination and using different elastomers entirely, however, the substrate was kept constant throughout. To further reinforce any frictional benefit following from fluorination, dissimilar surfaces (i.e. different roughness, hardness, etc.) can be adopted.

- The elastomer sample, using a scalpel, were cut to the required dimension of 20x20mm by hand. The actual size will be 20 ± 1 mm on each side as a rule was used to determine this dimension. Therefore, the preparation to undertake the experimental tests may have altered the sample inadvertently, Consequently, this can be improved by adopting a stamp to obtain the elastomer from the provided standard elastomer sheet, this will provide a uniform and consistent dimension.

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Appendix:
Macro Friction Raw Results

FKM 2, LEVEL 0 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

Isolating each test

FKM 2, LEVEL 9 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

FKM 2, Level 9, 0.1mm/s

FKM 2, Level 9, 1mm/s

FKM 8, LEVEL 0 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

Isolating each test

Isolating each test

FKM 8, LEVEL 5 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

Isolating each test

Isolating each test

FKM 8, LEVEL 9 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

FKM 8, Level 9, 0.1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 1mm/s

Isolating each test

Isolating each test

FKM 8, Level 9, 0.1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 0.1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 0.1mm/s

FKM 8, Level 9, 1mm/s

NBR 10, LEVEL 0 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

NBR 10, Level 0, 0.1mm/s

1mm/s Sliding Speed

NBR 10, Level 0, 1mm/s

Isolating each test

NBR 10, Level 0, 1mm/s

NBR 10, Level 0, 1mm/s

NBR 10, Level 0, 1mm/s

NBR 10, LEVEL 5 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

NBR 10, LEVEL 9 FLUORINATION

0.1mm/s Sliding Speed

1mm/s Sliding Speed

SECTION B-B

Threaded Hole to Suit M12 Bolt

Aluminium 1 1/4 bar
 Drilled and tapped to suit M12 Bolt

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:				FINISH:		DEBUR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
DRAWN				NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:	
CHK'D										INSTRON ADAPTER	
APPV'D											
MFG										DWG NO. MAT7400-001 REV B A3	
Q.A										SCALE:2:1	
								MATERIAL: ALUMINIUM		SHEET 1 OF 1	
								WEIGHT:			

SECTION B-B
SCALE 1.2 : 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:				FINISH:		DEBUR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION C	
DRAWN NM				SIGNATURE NM		DATE 17/11/16		TITLE: DISC ADAPTER			
CHK'D NM				SIGNATURE NM		DATE 17/11/16		DWG NO. MAT7400-002 REV C			
APPV'D NM				SIGNATURE NM		DATE 17/11/16					
MFG				MATERIAL: ALUMINIUM		WEIGHT:		SCALE:1:1		SHEET 1 OF 1	
Q.A										A3	

(A) THREADED HOLES TO SUIT M10 BOLTS

(B) $\phi 11$

DETAILS OF CIRCULAR HOLES 8-OFF (A)

- 1. PCD: 80mm
- 2. THREADED HOLES AND SUIT M10 BOLT
- 3. CENTRE OF PATTERN OCCURS AT CENTRE OF PLATE

DETAILS OF OUTER HOLES 4-OFF (B)

- 1. HOLE DIAMETER 11MM

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS				FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION B	
SURFACE FINISH:											
TOLERANCES:											
LINEAR:											
ANGULAR:											
		NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:			
DRAWN		NM		NM		17/11/16		BASE HOLDING PLATE			
CHK'D		NM		NM		17/11/16					
APPV'D		NM		NM		17/11/16					
MFG											
Q.A								MATERIAL:		DWG NO.	
								ALUMINIUM		MAT7400-003 REV B	
								WEIGHT:		SCALE:1:2	
										SHEET 1 OF 1	
										A3	

8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

F
E
D
C
B
A

SURFACE ROUGHNESS ON A SINGLE SIDE TO BE XXXXX

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION		
DRAWN			NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE: SLIDING PLATE OF DEFINED SURFACE		
CHK'D											
APPV'D											
MFG											
Q.A									MATERIAL: STAINLESS STEEL		DWG NO. MAT7400-004 REV A
									WEIGHT:		A3
									SCALE:1:2		SHEET 1 OF 1

8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

F
E
D
C
B
A